

Masters Thesis – In Defense of a Masters in Health Sciences
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A critical review of cell-free microRNA-141 in the development of prognostic and diagnostic tools for prostate cancer.

Abstract:

MicroRNA-141 in circulating bodily fluid has been subject to intense investigation since 2008 when cell-free miR-141 was found to be elevated in the serum of patients with prostate cancer. It has been demonstrated in numerous studies that cfmiR-141 is elevated in circulating bodily fluids of many patients with late stage prostate cancer, yet there is no conclusive data in regards to specific changes in intracellular miR-141 concentration over the course of PrCa progression. Assuming refinement of analytical methods for miRNA quantification, it is evident that cfmiR-141 could be developed as part of prognostic tools to study and better inform clinicians of treatment efficacy in late stage prostate cancer. However, due to the fields limited understanding of miR-141 transcript targeting, regulatory mechanisms, and the process by which miR-141 enters the circulation, it is still unclear whether or not cell-free miR-141 can be implemented as a diagnostic tool for clinical use. Furthermore, it is also unclear what valuable diagnostic information is conveyed by the detection of cell-free miR-141 in bodily fluids. Therefore, this paper is designed to provide a conceptual analysis of the potential diagnostic uses for cfmiRNA-141 in regards to progression of late-stage prostate cancer and metastatic disease, including technological challenges that will be faced in development of diagnostic tools to study cfmiRNA.

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Introduction

Discovery of miRNAs

In 1993 Lee et al and Wightman et al published landmark discoveries in the field of non-coding RNAs after identifying *lin-4*^{1,2} as a Lin-14 regulator and likely 3'-untranslated region-binding, time-dependent, down-regulator of *lin-14* mRNA during the development of *Caenorhabditis elegans*. This sparked a series of investigations in the field including those published in 2000 by Ruvkun lab identifying *let-7* as a “heterochronic switch gene” and later describing and recognizing *let-7* as an important miRNA.³ In 2001 Gary Ruvkun provided a review of three important publications in the field of newly coined “microRNAs” in the journal *Science*. The name of the article- “*Glimpses of a Tiny RNA World*” revealed Ruvkun’s and many others’ fascination with this newly discovered RNA structure and the important functions it plays in the cells of a broad range of organisms.⁴ The three back-to-back *Science* publications from Tuschl⁵, Bartel⁶, and Ambros⁷ serve as the second notable landmark in the field of miRNAs. In 2001, inventory was taken from the three groups that identified almost 100 miRNAs from *Drosophila*, HeLa cells, and *C. elegans*. By 2008, Griffiths-Jones et al⁸ had catalogued over 5922 miRNA from essentially every known biological Kingdom, as well as viruses, suggesting a drastically high level of conservation. To date, the most credible sequence Database – “miRBase” - has expanded, with a released version in 2014 including 30424 “mature miRNA products” from 206 species and counting.⁹

Bartel correctly proposed a distinctive hairpin structures that differentiated miRNAs from other small non-coding RNAs such as small interfering RNA and Piwi-interacting RNA, which were identified with many miRNAs in the early 2000s and thought to be involve in similar RNA silencing functions.^{10,11,12,13} Nomenclature for miRNAs was later developed¹² and has been

generally accepted such that miRNA precursors (pri-miRNA) are transcribed from the human genome and later processed into pre-miRNA, then the small ~22nt sequences called mature mircoRNA (miRNA), or “miR-141” for example when referring to a specific miRNA. The coding sequence that is transcribed to pri-miRNA of a given miRNA such as miR-141 is signified as MIR-141.

While many teams were identifying and cataloging miRNAs, studies undertaken by Mello and Fire earned them the 2006 Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine¹⁴ and laid the foundation for studies such as Hammond et al and Bernstein et al wherein the proteins responsible for processing MIR to miRNA and carrying out their function were beginning to be revealed more clearly.^{15,16} As the molecular mechanisms of miRNA-induced translational regulation were beginning to be uncovered, and miRNAs and their respective gene loci were being identified, other teams had been fueling the excitement around miRNAs by demonstrating a role for miRNA in cellular homeostasis, and a likely relationship between miRNA regulation and the development of cancer.¹⁷ Shortly after human miRNA were being discovered, Calin et al reported a high incidence of B-cell chronic lymphocytic leukemias among patients that have a deletion or downregulation of miR-15 and miR-16.¹⁸ The same group reported strong associations between particular MIRs and cancer, suggesting that MIRs are often located at fragile gene loci,¹⁸ but it wasn't until 2009 that evidence of miRNA dysregulation causing cancer *in vivo* was reported. At this time the Croce lab reported upregulation of miR-155 influencing their mouse model to develop acute lymphoblastic leukemia/high-grade lymphoma.¹⁹ *In vivo* studies such as these continued. Models of cancer biology had to be rethought as new discoveries were made such as the capability of cancer cells to become oncomiR addicted in studies by

Medina et al.²⁰ These discoveries set the stage for many investigations to come, and the field of microRNAs in cancer has continued to grow ever since.²¹

Around the same time that the first *in vivo* evidence of miRNA dysregulation in cancer was being reported, miRNA was shown to be present and detectable in many bodily fluids, most notably the blood.^{22,23,24,25} Although it was unknown at the time how cell-free miRNA (cfmiRNA) were stable from RNase degradation and thus detectable in blood samples, investigators quickly recognized the biomarker and therapeutic potential.²² This sparked continued investigations, which appear to be ongoing to date (Figure 1). It was later identified that cfmiRNA could be encapsulated by extracellular vesicles or bound by Argonaute proteins in the circulation, which is shown to confer resistance to RNase degradation.²⁶ Discovery of cfmiRNA though to be encapsulated in extracellular vesicles raised many questions about the functionality and source of these vesicles.²⁷ Since, it has been suggested that a particular form of extracellular vesicles termed “exosomes” containing cfmiRNA may serve as more valuable samples for biomarker development than crude blood extracts implemented in many studies.²⁸ Trends in the number of publications since 2008 (Figure 1) reinforce that this proposition has affected the field of cancer research and that exosomes are gaining particular attention for biomarker development.²⁹ Studies on cfmiRNA independently may be on a partial hiatus until effective methods for identifying tissue of exosomal origin are refined. Furthermore, what appears to be a trend of decreasing publications concerning miRNA and cancer, both in 2016 and in projections for 2017, may be due to the many challenges that are being faced while studying the complex nature of miRNA in cancer in diagnostic or therapeutic tools.^{28,29}

Figure 1: Publications of miRNA and exosomes in the study of Cancer 2008-current

Figure 1: Quantification of the number of publications per year since 2008 for Series 1- Exosomes and cancer versus circulating microRNA and cancer (PubMed query: circulating miRNA AND cancer; compared with exosomes AND cancer; accessed April 2017). Similar trends can be seen between PubMed query: “extracellular vesicles AND cancer” as compared to “exosomes AND cancer.”

Significance

Cancer can arise from many forms of dysregulation of innumerable molecular pathways involved in gene expression and cell division.³⁰ MiRNAs are key regulators in gene expression and therefore it is expected that an imbalance in miRNA for any particular reason would disrupt the typical function of a cell and potentially lead to cancer^{30,31} as depicted in Figure 2.³² Furthermore, It has been suggested that approximately half of the human gene products are regulated by miRNA.³³

Figure 2: Conventional model for oncomiRs and tumor suppress miRs in Cancer

Figure 2: A conventional model of miRNA regulation in normal (healthy) cells and cancer cells. Image source: *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 2017;18(3):507.³²

As medical communities begin adapting personalized medical practices, oncology is likely going to be one of the first fields to adapt personalized approaches as common practice.³⁴ Biomarkers and respective technologies are going to play an important role in the implementation of personalized medical approaches at essentially every level from screening and diagnosis, to indicators of therapy response and prognosis.³⁴

Improved molecular and biochemical methods in order to identify and analyze human molecular markers has broadened the definition and capabilities of clinicians. With new and powerful tools, the biomedical “Omics” movement has begun to usher in an era personalized medicine in which clinicians will be learning to better survey and detect markers of disease, biomonitor, classify patients into groups predicted to respond better to therapies, and most importantly prevent disease.^{35,36} Ideally, advancement of technologies to detect miRNAs could lead to early detection of disease in which intervention and therapies such as RNAi technologies may be more specifically targeted than current therapies, and thus more effective. Many biomedical researchers, clinicians, and patients are attracted to the prospect of cfmiRNA serving as an early

indicator of cancer. Implementing miRNA studies into a personalized medical approach would be particularly useful due to the high level of complexity and unique nature of cancer.³⁴ Many of the current screening procedure and medical decision making processes are based on centuries-old epidemiological and clinical data on effective diagnostics and treatment for large populations, whereas the medical community is beginning to call for effective, more individualized treatment options. As computational techniques are refined and the healthcare industry gains access to powerful tools for collection and processing of large bio-datasets from patients, lowly-personalized treatments such as pharmaceutical chemotherapy drugs can be replaced by more targeted and less systemically harmful treatment options.³⁴ Although early detection would be particularly useful in designing treatments or preventing progression of highly lethal disease such as lung cancer, addressing difficulties in staging and accurate prognosis are likely to be the initial steps in development of cfmiRNA tools.^{37,38,39} Specifically, the need for a “liquid biopsy” or non-invasively obtained biomarkers is apparent for prostate cancer diagnosis and staging due to inadequacies of Prostate specific antigen (PSA) and digital rectal examinations (DRE) in the clinical setting.^{40,41}

Candidate cancers in which biomarker development would be useful and practical could be thought of as those with a high incidence, low survival-rate, a difficult or inadequate screening process, often localized, resourcefully demanding, with restricted availability of screening procedure or therapy for the cancer type, and a high burden on quality of life.⁴² Lung cancer would seem to be a prime candidate based on this criteria but it could be argued that smoking cessation is the first barrier that public health and medical professionals must address in the treatment of lung cancer before considering the need for a diagnostic tool that may also elicit

insight to the etiology of a tissue-specific cancer. Breast cancer fits many of the criteria discussed, including being the second most common form of cancer death in the United States (Table 1) but there still exists large and widespread reproducibility issue in the field of cfmiRNA as biomarkers in breast cancer.²⁸ This isn't to say that sex-specific populations of patients with cancer should be removed from consideration. On the contrary, due to more readily targetable populations for clinical study recruitment and repeated demonstration of differential cfmiRNA levels between opposite sexes,⁴³ sex-specific cancers should be preferentially selected for initial cfmiRNA biomarker development. Thus prostate cancer is the most fitting candidate, being the second most common cause of cancer death in men in the United States (Table 1), a clearly targetable population for testing cfmiRNA biomarkers in the clinic. Biomarkers for prognosis, detection, or proper staging would all have high utility.

Table 1: Estimated Number of Deaths for the Four Major Cancers by Sex and Age Group, 2017

	<u>All ages</u>	<u>Younger than 45</u>	<u>45 and Older</u>	<u>Younger than 65</u>	<u>65 and Older</u>
All sites					
Male	318,420	8,730	309,690	98,580	219,840
Female	282,500	9,810	272,690	85,580	196,920
Colon & rectum					
Male	27,150	960	26,190	9,470	17,680
Female	23,110	700	22,410	6,260	16,850
Lung & bronchus					
Male	84,590	690	83,900	24,510	60,080
Female	71,280	690	70,590	18,970	52,310
Breast (female)	40,610	2,320	38,290	16,800	23,810
Prostate	26,730	*	*	2,900	23,830

*Estimate for men <45 years is fewer than 50 deaths.

Projected deaths are based on US mortality data from 2000 to 2014, National Center for Health Statistics, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.
Note: Estimates should not be compared with those from previous years.

American Cancer Society, Surveillance Research, 2017

Table 1: Current estimations of cancer related deaths in the US, adapted from the American Cancer Society, 2017.⁴⁴

In a 2016 review of PrCa detection and prognosis, Filella and Foj report that although 74 cfmiRNAs have been reported to have biomarker potential in PrCa, only 25 of those cfmiRNA have been reported as detectable and useful as biomarkers, miR-141 and miR-375 having the greatest number of validated studies supporting their biomarker potential in PrCa.⁴⁵ Furthermore, the miR-200 family is of the most widely studied and reported miRNA in cancer and research.⁴⁵ Therefore it could be assumed that if any miRNA were going to be the next in line for clinically valuable PrCa biomarker development with currently existent data, a combination profile of miRNA to include miR-141 would be a prime candidate.⁴⁶ The low-to-moderate abundance of cfmiR-141 in human serum samples prior to mutagenesis further qualifies cfmiR-141 as a prime candidate for development of diagnostic and prognostic tools for the study and treatment of PrCa because elevation in a low-to-moderately abundant cfmiRNA would thus indicate a detectable change in the cancer that can readily be distinguished from a healthy cell.²⁸

Although previous studies have attempted to demonstrate the diagnostic utility of cfmiR-141, further experimentation will have to be conducted and the source of cfmiR-141 in non-invasively obtained bodily fluids will have to be revealed before implementation as a diagnostic tool.

Background

Biogenesis

Many transcription factors (TFs) are often required to initiate transcription of a MIR, which can be thought to begin when RNA Pol II associates with the MIR. RNA Pol II generates pri-miRNAs.⁴⁷ Pri-miRNAs possess a 5' cap and poly-A tail, much like any pre-mRNA transcript in the nucleus would.^{47,48} In order for pri-miRNAs to exit the nucleus, they must first be processed by a complex of proteins including Drosha, and Pasha, and DiGeorge Syndrome Critical Region Gene 8 protein, together often referred to as a microprocessor.⁴⁹ This results in pre-miRNA, an ~70nt in length nucleic acid, often with a distinctive stem-loop structure that can then be exported from the nucleus by way of interactions with nuclear protein exportin 5 and RanGTP.⁵⁰ In the cytoplasm, pre-miRNA interacts with Dicer, a protein known to play a dual role, completing aspects of miRNA processing, and initiating the formation of the RNA-induced silencing complex (RISC).^{16,51} During initial interactions between miRNA and Dicer, the large protein complex catalyzes ~70nt long pre-miRNA into a double stranded form of mature miRNA of ~22nts in length, referred to previously as miRNA. Dicer is then thought to carry the double stranded miRNA, and recruit Argonaute (AGO) proteins to form the RISC in which a single strand of the miRNA guides the complex to target mRNA for regulatory purposes⁵¹ as depicted in Figure 3. When the miRNA loaded RISC complex base pairs, most often partially and imperfectly, with a complementary 3' UTR-region of an mRNA, AGO proteins can cleave the miRNA:mRNA double stranded nucleic acid structure, leading to degradation of the miRNA and mRNA, or the protein complex can simply occupy the mRNA in order to inhibit translation.⁵²

Figure 3: Illustration of miRNA biogenesis and intracellular function

Figure 3: a conventional model of miRNA processing in healthy cells.

pri-miRNA synthesized by RNA Pol II, processed by DGCR8, Drosha, and exported from the nucleus by Exportin-5 bound by RanGTP, then processed from pre-miRNA to mature miRNA in which the short miRNA can translationally repress or degrade mRNA targets based on RISC association and base pairing.

Image Source: *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol.* 2013;14(8):475-488.⁵³

In regards to biomarker development, the biogenesis of miRNA is important in understanding the features of a miRNA that may play a role in cellular function of healthy or cancerous cells. For example, increased concentration of a miRNA can indicate the inactivation of miRNA rather than increase targeting (because miRNA targeting with RISC complex often results in target mRNA and miRNA degradation). Hypothetically, each process mediated by genes of miRNA processing that is integrally involved in generation and regulation of miRNA has the potential for mutagenesis and potentially lack of repair in an oncogenic microenvironment. Because miRNAs are intimately involved in cellular homeostasis it would be expected that the heterogeneous and often unpredictable nature of cancer would be reflected into the pool of miRNA of any given

cancerous cell. By this logic, if a consistent feature or function involved in miRNA regulation were discovered, resulting in a unique molecular signature as indication of the feature or function, that molecular signal would serve as a powerful biomarker of cellular homeostasis at the transcriptional level. A transcriptional biomarker would be valuable in the clinician's diagnostic armamentarium because it stands in middle ground of the central dogma of biology and disease. Proteins and gene mutations are often studied in a clinical setting but mRNA is needed in order to further reveal the networks of gene regulation and protein expression that is characteristically studied in a systems biology approach to diagnostics, oncology, and personalized medicine.⁵⁴ Although a high level of specificity is not expected of all biomarkers, cancer is a highly complex disease that likely requires such specificity in order to be properly implemented in the progressive field of personalized medicine.⁴² Therefore, basic knowledge of source and function of miRNA are integral to the design and development of methods to detect and draw meaningful conclusions about disease conditions such as those in cancer.

Intracellular and Extracellular miRNA

Intracellular function of MiRNA

MicroRNAs are classified into families based on gene loci or seed sequence homology, which makes sense in the light of known mechanisms of miRNA-mediated gene regulation discussed above.⁵⁵ Base pairing between ribonucleic acids is thought to be the basis of interactions between miRNA and their respective targets. To classify miRNA by sequence homology would appear to convey functional similarity, although this has been debated.^{56,57} It is also important to note that miRNA family members such as the miR-200 family members reside on different chromosomal loci yet respond to many of the same promoters in order to transcribe pri-miRNA^{58,59,60} as

depicted in Figure 4. Thus the discussion of the function of miR-141 would be incomplete without a discussion of the microRNA-200 family (referred to here as miR-200s) and their interconnectedness.^{55,61}

Mir-200s have been shown to co-regulate with some of the TFs that miR-200s target demonstrated in Figure 4.^{62,63} This is further supported by recent findings that suggest a complete cellular loss of miR-200s after modifications of their gene promoter regions.⁶⁴ The major players in miR-200 regulation are thought to be the zinc finger e-box bind homeobox 1 (ZEB1) and 2 (ZEB2) as promoter inhibitors, and Specificity protein 1 as well as p53 as promoters of expression.^{59,60,61} As seen in Figure 4, each cluster of miR-200s, namely miR-141, 200, 200a, 200b, and 429 can target ZEB 1 and 2 (ZEB1/2) mRNA for regulation in the presence of the RISC.⁶⁵ More importantly, all of the miR-200s were shown to be involved in tumor suppression in unspecific prostate tissue, and it is thought that miR-200s accomplish this by inhibiting epithelial to mesenchymal transition (EMT)- a healthy cell function during embryogenesis⁶⁶ but crucial step in initiation of PrCa malignancy and metastasis when dysregulated.⁶⁷ Recent research indicates that loss of miR-200 expression can occur by mutagenesis, and that in vitro cell lines deficient in p53 when exposed to EMT-promoting carcinogens are more likely to develop a malignant phenotype deficient in E-cadherin- a protein shown to play an integral role in epithelial morphology and cell adherence that is altered in some way in metastatic tissues.⁶⁸ Although miR-200s have been shown to affect protein expression at almost every defined step of metastasis, miR-141 has been shown to have particular involvement in EMT mainly by downregulating E-cadherin expressional inhibiting TFs- ZEB1/2 which in turn regulates miR-

200s and the production of vimentin- another protein shown enhance cell migration and metastatic capabilities.^{69,70,71}

Figure 4: Co-regulatory functions of miR-200s and ZEB1/2

Figure 4: Illustrative depiction of miR-200 family affects on ZEB1/2 expression and co-regulation with miR-200s, E-cadherin, and regulation of EMT. MiR-141 may also be responsible for TGF-β mRNA regulation independent of other miR-200 family members. Image source: *Oncogene* (2010) **29**, 937–948; doi:10.1038/onc.2009.406.⁶⁵

Aside from regulating ZEB1/2, recent studies have shown that miR-200s also suppress expression of moesin, PKCα, and target hundreds of sub-networks of mRNAs involved in

cytoskeletal homeostasis that is characteristic of epithelial cell morphology although these findings were not entirely validated in prostate cell lines.⁷² Nevertheless, studies by Bracken et al demonstrates a much more complex network of miR-200 activity and regulation than the model depicted in Figure 4.

The most recent published studies have placed focus on a segment of the computationally generated gene targets first reported by Bracken et al, that were partially included and validated in by Liu et al, suggesting that a series of gene regulatory networks including regulation of E-cadherin can increase the number of CTCs originating from PrCa tissue both in cell lines and within in vivo mouse models.⁷³ In the same study Liu et al. suggested that miR-141 upregulation confers a metastasis-suppressing effect in PC3, DU145, and LAPC9 cell cultures, and human PrCa derived CD44⁺ cells thought to be involved in metastasis from PrCa stem cells, and decreased incidence of lung metastasis from xenographed PrCa cells in their mouse model. In contrast, Li et al recently showed that intracellular miR-141 positively regulated cell proliferation in PC3 cell lines while studying the relationship between miR-141 target genes and stemness of PrCa cells.⁷⁴ These two most recent papers by Liu et al and Li et al demonstrate the current state of studies conducted on intracellular function of miR-141, a state of discordance which is also representative of many of the previous studies of cfmiR-141 discussed in later sections. Predicting and validating mapped targets for miR-141 in independent studies does not seem to provide a comprehensive rationale for discordant findings in PrCa and mPrCa in vitro studies.

It is apparent that there is either a problem with in vivo miR-141 experimental methodology and/or a more complex process miR-141 regulation in cell proliferation, metastasis, and expression of stemness taking place than previously thought. Currently there is no resolution on the significance of misregulated miR-141 in the heterogeneous populations of PrCa cells, and it appears that if cfmiR-141 could in some way target a distant cell to initiate metastasis or “prime” a tissue microenvironment for metastasis by PrCa CTCs, the effect of cfmiR-141 entering a distant cell would depend on that cell's current state.⁷⁵ The phenomenon of miRNA duality function reported previously^{76,77} wherein many miRNA have different effects when forcefully upregulated or placed in varied tissue types appears to hold true even among different types of cancer cells in a heterogeneous population of PrCa cells.

In considering a new paradigm in the study of miRNA, the diagram in Figure 4 depicts the cellular membrane as dotted for purposes of depicting the permeable nature of the cell membrane in comparison to the nuclear membrane but the depiction can be taken to describe a much more interesting dynamic of intracellular functions vs. extracellular functions. Although the intracellular and extracellular aspects of miR-141 are discussed in this paper, the line between intracellular miR-141 function cfmiR-141 source or function quickly blurs when considering the idea that cfmiR-141 likely exchanges messages to its neighboring cells (analogous with paracrine signaling), and potentially even signals distant cells (analogous to exocrine signaling). Cortez et al went as far as to describe miRNA as hormones.⁷⁶ The intracellular vs, extracellular line blurs even further when considering the implications of downregulated miR-141 disinhibiting in some way EMT and metastasis. Metastatic cells add another component of movement because they themselves can travel in order to physically interact with neighboring tissues but they likely also

release cfmiR-141 along with other molecular signals after travelling at varying distances throughout the body.⁸⁰ Furthermore, it has been shown that EMT hybrids generated *in vivo* from some forms of miR-141 dysregulation have increased invasion and metastatic potential.^{78,79} It has been implied that circulating EMT hybrids excrete miR-200s in EVs to the cells they interact with and those cells can then become EMT hybrids, further increasing the likelihood that EMT hybrid cells will initiate metastatic colonization or that a metastatic colony will form because the primary EMT hybrids have now created a secondary extracellular and intracellular environment that is conducive in some ways of cancer development. The matter of EMT has been complicated further when it was demonstrated that all miR-200s could be transferred between cells of differing metastatic tendencies while miR-141/200c instigated extravasation events, but all miR-200s suppressed early metastatic events. Humpheres et al concludes their review in stating that relationship between miR-200s and PrCa have not been thoroughly investigated but deserves more attention, further shedding doubt on the current diagnostic value of detectable cfmiR-141.⁷⁸

Extracellular miR-141

Extracellular vesicles

Although there doesn't appear to be much resolution on the formal terminology for extracellular membrane-bound organelles, extracellular vesicles (EVs) will be used to describe those membranous vesicles of diameters between 40-1000nm, accepting convention of Penforis et al.⁸¹ Although the biological importance of the many types of EVs is still unclear, the process of EV formation is highly conserved in both prokaryotes and eukaryotes, and hypervesiculation has been documented in many forms of cancer making it a particularly interesting area of study.⁸²

EVs are believed to originate from either apoptotic cells which tend to give rise to relatively larger EVs, cellular membrane blebbing (often referred to as ectosomes), or release of the plasma membrane in small vesicles often referred to as exosomes, all of which have been shown to contain miRNA.^{83,84,85} Exosomes have been shown to bud directly from the plasma membrane, outward into the extracellular space or be released as small vesicles called multivesicular bodies (MVBs), arising from inward budding of a plasma membrane endosome, which are then released into the extracellular space.⁸⁶

EVs can be released by cells into the extracellular space in response to stress, death, malignant transformation, chemotherapy, and radiotherapies.⁸⁷ Ectosomes are released from the cellular membrane whereas exosomes are released only after part of the cell membrane is endocytosed, therefore it is reasonable to think that ectosome production is affected by cell membrane cholesterol content and components of lipid rafts⁸⁸ whereas exosome production is affected at least during initial formation by coat proteins such as clathrin.⁸⁹ It is believed that the ubiquitin signaled endosomal sorting complexes required for transport (ESCRT) pathway may play a role in packaging and export of EVs containing miRNA. Furthermore this may be a regular cellular function of the ESCRT cellular machinery that results in release of EVs^{90,91} although there are as many aspects of this hypothesis to be tested as there are ambiguities surrounding the reason EVs are released into the circulation (summary of extracellular vesicles in Figure 4 below). One of the few functions that EV biogenesis has been shown to play a role in cellular function is that of a defensive secretory system. One example of exosomes utilized by healthy cells as a defensive tactic, and potential process for dysfunction in unhealthy cells, was demonstrated by Pilzer et al

in which membrane attack complexes could be ectocytosed or endocytosed and processed into MVBs for exosome release in order to protect the cell from complement-mediated cell death.⁸⁸ Interestingly, this EV mediated selection and exportation has been shown to expand the cells range of molecules that can be secreted such as those without Golgi localization sequences, or insoluble proteins.^{92,93,94,95} Understanding the molecular basis for selective encapsulation of genetic material, and detection of that genetic material that indicates the tissue-of-origin has obvious and powerful implications in the study of PrCa diagnosis and treatment. Increasing evidence in the field of EVs is being obtained that demonstrate biological importance of EVs and the likely role they have in PrCa.

Figure 5: Illustration of extracellular vesicle formation

Figure 4: Illustration of sources of extracellular bodies containing cfmiRNA in the circulation. Image depicts (a) pathways regularly involved in exosomal release, (b) membrane blebbing and golgi vesicle release under normal conditions, and (c) release of apoptotic bodies into extracellular environment. (Image source: *Nature Reviews Urology* **11**, 688–701(2014).⁹⁶

Researchers have been able to characterize many aspects of EVs from size to membrane protein content, to intravesicular protein lipid and genetic content, but separating, differentiating, and identifying where EVs have originated has been a continuing challenge.²⁸ Technical limitations of studying EVs is in part due to their heterogeneity in size, physiological origin, and composition, but also due to the methods that are common in the field of molecular biology that appear too mechanically harsh to maintain the EV structure during isolation procedures such as centrifugation.^{97,98,99,100} Nevertheless, a recent study by Park et al demonstrates a novel method by which prostate specific EVs (prostasomes) can be isolated and differentiated from other circulating EVs by adapting a method of immunoprecipitation utilizing a prostate specific membrane antigen.⁸²

This could provide a snap shot of what is specifically going on in the prostate at a particular time, although it is hard to say how long prostasomes remain in circulation, and it is still unknown why prostasomes are released. Therefore, it is unclear which aspects of the cellular environment the prostatesome informs a researcher or clinician of. The idea of obtaining a sample of the cellular contents from EVs is complex. This is evident when considering the current model of MVB formation in which it seems that endosomes can travel throughout different regions of the cell and bud to form smaller vesicles that contain cytoplasmic contents of specific regions and cell types, yet it is known that exosomes do not contain a random sample of biomolecules from that cell. Rather, there appears to be a set of biomolecules that are encapsulated in EVs distinct to each class of lipids, proteins, and genetic material.^{101,102,103,104} More recently, Villarroya-Beltri et al identified a protein, hnRNPA2B1, that when sumoylated and existing in wild-type form is active in sorting miRNAs to exosomes.¹⁰⁵ HnRNPA2B1 is one of many biomolecules involved

in miRNA regulation and sorting into exosomes, and regulation of release of those exosomes. None of these findings were investigated in PrCa lines or prostasomes. These findings do not necessarily generate hope that previous data on the detection of elevated cfmiR-141 in PrCa will be validated, but rather usher in a new set of criteria and tools for attempts to better understand what earlier studies that cfmiR-141 seem to have revealed- elevated in bodily fluids due to prostasome release by PrCa cells.

Argonaute bound miRNA

Argonaute 2 (AGO2) can carry cfmiRNA and it is generally accepted that this miR-AGO2 complex is excreted from a variety of cells rather than assembled after entering the circulation.¹⁰⁷ It has also been shown that these miR-AGO2 complexes are resistant to RNase degradation in the circulation which is reinforced by the knowledge that miRNA would degrade in the cell or blood in a matter of seconds to minutes if it were not bound to RBPs.²² Investigators tend to agree that AGO-complexing or EV-encapsulation confers protection from proteases and RNases.²⁶

Using a CRISPR-Cas9 screen to overcome many experimental difficulties, Golden et al showed that AGO2 kinases play a more specific role in miRNA-mediated repression than previously thought.¹⁰⁸ The ANKRD52-PPP6C phosphatase complex and CSNK1A1 kinase are at least partly responsible for complementary dephosphorylation-phosphorylation of AGO2 respectively.¹⁰⁸ Phosphorylation and dephosphorylation events were shown to occur at the highly conserved S824-S834 amino acid sequence, which was shown to regulate AGO:miRNA affinity in the cellular environment. This new finding by Golden et al, as well as knowledge of the AGO-

miRNA protective effect mentioned above reveals a molecular underpinning of miRNA expression regulation and miRNA-mediated gene silencing that may be exploited to study tissue-specific miRNA expression. Studies by Golden et al should be followed up in a similar cell line known to activate the ANKRD52-PPP6C complex and CSNK1A1 kinase in order to determine which, if any, of the AGO2 phosphorylation events occur on AGO2-miRNA that is sequestered into prostasomes. Furthermore, it should be examined whether or not this activity is unique to tissue state (i.e. cancerous vs. healthy samples), assuming that the ANKRD52-PPP6C and CSNK1A1 activities are not directly affected by the pathological state. This finding demonstrated the potential of isolating and studying AGO2 bound cfmiR-141 with unique phosphorylation signals in bodily fluids rather than having to isolate prostasomes for study because AGO bound miRNA has been shown to constitute more of the cfmiRNA content than EVs in blood.¹⁰⁹ Although there is a possibility to exploit potentially unique post-translational modifications of AGO-miRNA complexes in the circulation as indicators of tissue of origin, this field is far from answering many of the questions necessary for such a technique to make it into clinical level studies with human PrCa patients.

Variability in EV content and AGO bound miRNA among various studies

Melo et al has recently reported that exosomes from breast cancer cells are equipped with pre-miRNAs and all cellular machinery such as Dicer, AGO2, and TRBP, required to process pre-miRNA into respective miRNA.¹¹⁰ Melo et al go on to demonstrate that after fusion of breast cancer exosomes, a rapid silencing of the target cell mRNA is initiated, affecting the cellular environment in a manner that may promote tumor growth. These and many other studies address a large body of knowledge about miRNA processing, expression, packaging and activity that is

still unclear. Therefore while analyzing prostasomes, care should be taken to comprehensively sequence the RNA content including both miR-141 and precursors of miR-141.

The lack of knowledge regarding EV generation and potential functions in circulation do not support a reasonable expectation that a clear role of intracellular or cfmiR-141 in the progression of PrCa will be uncovered for the purposes of treating PrCa before the molecular basis of miRNA activity, regulation, and encapsulation is further elucidated. Although the role cfmiR-141 may not be clear, it is important that investigations continue. There is promise that if miRNAs alone will not suffice as biomarkers, biomolecules and regulatory networks involved in miRNA biogenesis, processing, and packaging can be accurately monitored as indicators of pathophysiological conditions such as PrCa progression.

The fields of intracellular miRNA function and sources of cfmiRNA are progressing to the point at which basic science and technological advancements may be enabling translational science to design and implement miR-141 as a diagnostic tool, identifying source of cfmiR-141 being a major stumbling block in the past decade. Analysis of previous studies in miR-141, often referred to as “the case of miR-141” reveal potentially valuable information about the process of PrCa development and potentially more specifically, the development of mPrCa. The obvious prognostic value of cfmiR-141 and large body of studies that have confirmed elevated levels of cfmiR-141 in serum of patients with advanced PrCa show promise that there is a pathophysiological underpinning of metastatic disease to be monitored via cfmiR-141 detection (reviewed in Table 2).

CfmiR-141 and prostate cancer

The miR-141 controversy

Much of the debate around cfmiRNA and its use as a biomarker in prostate cancer (PrCa) point to what has been referred to as “the case of miR-141.”²⁸ The first evidence of miR-141 differential presence in PrCa versus healthy tissue was reported by Porkka et al in 2007.¹¹¹ In 2008 Mitchell et al conducted a study on cfmiRNA that has become a hallmark of the field.²² Mitchell et al. demonstrated that serum miR-141 could be used differentiate between human patients with PrCa and healthy controls in their study population. This was a particularly powerful study because Mitchell et al conducted proof of principle experiments to introduce xenografted human cancerous epithelial tissue specific to the prostate into mice, which then increased miR-141 conc. in sera. It is important to note that the study by Mitchell et al included healthy controls and patients who had been diagnosed with metastatic prostate cancer (mPrCa). Although these findings are valuable and sparked a series of follow up studies, it did not provide insight as to the change in concentration of miR-141 throughout the development of PrCa lacking metastasis. In February 2011 Brase et al published the findings of a screening study on miRNA to investigate differential concentration in prostate cancer progression, demonstrating that miR-141 and miR-375 were the most significant indicators of increased risk of PrCa development.¹¹² These findings supported those of Mitchell et al and extended our understanding of changes in cfmiR-141 concentration through PrCa development. Brase et al further extended knowledge of miR-141 by comparing both localized PrCa and mPrCa to healthy controls, showing that intracellular miR-141 and cfmiR-141 were significantly elevated in both localized PrCa and more so in mPrCa groups when compared to health controls, suggesting that miR-141 may play a role in the development or progression of PrCa. Brase et al conclude that larger

studies of cfmiR-141 concentration in samples before and after surgical removal of prostatic tumor would need to be conducted, which subsequently took place in 2012 when Bryant et al reported finding significantly more serum-derived exosomes and microvesicles which conveyed greater cfmiR-141 concentration in a cohort of patients with metastatic disease following prostatectomy when compared to cfmiR-141 in patients with non-recurrent disease following prostatectomy. Of those papers that address miR-141 as a potential biomarker, many refer to the results published in May 2011 by a separate group who could not detect cfmiR-141 in their study population blood samples.¹¹³ Mahn et al. offers an explanation for this conflicting result:

“Mitchell et al used a pre-amplification step between reverse transcription and real-time PCR to increase the amount of low-abundant miRNAs; this methodological difference may explain our inability to detect *miR-141*.¹¹³”

Later in the 2011 paper by Mahn et al they also state:

“We did not compare patients with metastatic PCA with the other patient cohorts because of the small sample size (n = 8) and the clinical heterogeneity of these patients. However, circulating miRNA levels seemed to be similar to patients with clinically localized PCA.¹¹³”

Although Mahn et al responded to the conflicting results between their study and that of Mitchell et al, they do not directly offer reasoning for results contradictory to Brase et al- Namely, that Mahn et al could not detect cfmiR-141 nor did they report finding intracellular miR-141 in

patients with clinically localized PrCa pre-prostatectomy. It is likely that Mahn et al and Brase et al did not provide reasoning for discrepancies in their study findings because Mahn et al published their results only 3 months after Brase et al. Nevertheless, some explanation should be offered in regards to this considerable discrepancy in the field.

The small patient population with localized PrCa (n=10) from which tissue samples were collected, as well as some technical limitations, the discrepancy between Mahn et versus Mitchell et al can be rationalized. Mitchell et al classified miR-141 as a “moderate-lowly abundant miRNA” in healthy prostate tissue and circulation. Specifically, Mitchell et al was referring to plasma concentration and defined moderate-low abundance as 8,910 copies/ μ L-133,970 copies/ μ L. Therefore, pre-amplification steps implemented by Mitchell et al and Brase et al were essential to detecting miR-141 even when amplified 46-fold as reported by Mitchell et al. Neglecting the important difference that Mitchell et al and Brase et al studied cfmiRNA content in isolated serum samples for their studies and Mahn et al isolated plasma from samples in order to quantify cfmiRNA, Mahn et al implemented an implicit detection limit that would not allow for detection of miR-141 at healthy levels or even at 46-fold amplification.

Figure 6: Comparison of findings in the case of miR-141

Figure 6: intersection of findings reported in the initial landmark studies concerning cfmiR-141 in PrCa.

The initial controversy in the study of cfmiR-141 is representative of the controversy that exists in the field today. Although it appears that Mahn et al did not compose the study with a large enough population size or adequate methodological techniques to validate or refute the findings of Mitchell et al and Brase et al, Westermann et al conducted a study in a larger study population (n=70) in 2014 and showed that cfmiR-141 concentration was similar among patients with negative and positive biopsies. This finding is in agreement with the statement made by Mahn et al. that cfmiRNAs may be similar in patients with early stage PrCa, but it could also be due to the inadequacies of current PrCa biopsy techniques to sample the heterogeneous set of tissues in

the human prostate. Consistent with the findings of Mitchell et al and Brase et al, Westermann et al demonstrated that elevated cfmiR-141 concentration is correlated with higher Gleason scores, further validating the prognostic potential of cfmiR-141. It is important to mention that Westermann et al excluded all patients with mPrCa from the study, and excluded patients with potential benign prostate hyperplasia (BPH) from the controls during data analysis.

Westermann et al suggest that their results differ from previous findings in the field because previous studies possessed either small sample sizes, inadequate controls, large number of locally-advanced or metastatic PrCa, different methods in isolation, pre-amplification steps, conducting PCR, and spike-in or selection of reference genes or a combination of any of these sources of bias. Furthermore, Westermann et al advise that the field should agree upon standardized protocols for recruiting clinically-relevant study cohorts and experimental procedures in order to deduce accurate and applicable information about the diagnostic potential of cfmiRNA. Lastly, Westermann et al demonstrated a correlation between miR-141 and recurrence, grade, stage, and Gleason scores as separate measures, suggesting the biomarker potential of miR-141 in prognosis.

In order to better understand how cfmiRNAs, specifically cfmiR-141, could act as clinically valuable biomarkers, investigators set out to identify transcriptional targets, miRNA regulatory networks, sources of cfmiRNA, and potential functionality of cfmiRNA. Table 2 summarizes a selection of some of the most impactful findings in the field of cfmiRNA and PrCa. There appears to be a number of discrepancies surrounding cfmiR-141 detection, much like there was at the onset of this field. Nevertheless, it does appear that researchers in the field can agree that

elevated cfmiR-141 is associated with a higher-risk form of PrCa-involved disease, indicating the efficacy of cfmiR-141 as a prognostic tool.

Table 2: Summary of findings in the field of cfmiR-141 and PrCa

miRNA(s)	Bodily Fluid	Patient sample population(s)	Methods	Significant Finding	Reference	Year
miR-141	Serum	25 healthy patients compared with 25 patients with pre-diagnosed mPrCa	TaqMan RT-qPCR	Serum levels of miR-141 are elevated in mPrCa patients, as well as in some common epithelial cancers- breast, colon, and lung cancers	Mitchell et al	2008
mir-141	Serum	20 patients with primary PrCa secondary bone metastasis, 30 with localized PrCa, and 6 controls of benign prostate hyperplasia	TaqMan, RT-qPCR	MIR-141 elevated in mPrCa but no significant difference between levels in localized PrCa and BPH	Zhang et al	2011
miR-141, and 375	Serum	Initial comparison of 7 mPrCa patients, 14 localized PrCa patients. Two validation cohorts (total n=116) stratified by PrCa risk status	TaqMan RT-qPCR	Serum levels of miR-375 and miR-141 were elevated in patients with localized PrCa and more so in mPrCa. Degree of elevation also correlated with poorer prognosis	Brase et al	2011
miR-141, 375, and 378*	Serum	Comparison of 26 patients with mPrCa, 30 patients with high-risk localized PrCa, and 28 patients with low-risk localized PrCa	TaqMan miRNA microarrays and RT-qPCR	degree of elevated miRNA levels could be used to detect low-risk and late-stage mPrCa	Nguyen et al	2013
miR-141, 146b-3p, 194	Serum	Initial comparison of 8 PrCa patients with and 8 patients without relapse after prostatectomy. Validation cohort composed of 31 patients that experiences recurrence and 39 who did not	TaqMan RT-qPCR	miRNAs were elevated in PrCa patients who subsequently experienced post-prostatectomy rapid biochemical recurrence	Selth et al	2013
miR-141, 200a, 200c, 210, and 375	Serum	Initial comparisons of 25 patients with castration resistant PrCa post-prostatectomy and 25 healthy controls. Validation cohorts of 21 patients with PrCa and 20 healthy controls	TaqMan microarray and RT-qPCR	miRNAs were elevated in metastatic castration-resistant PrCa as compared to healthy controls	Cheng et al	2013
miR-141 and 21	Serum	38 PrCa patients undergoing prostatectomy compared with 40 healthy controls	Exiqon RT-qPCR	Initial upregulation post-prostatectomy believed to be due to surgically induced inflammation. Average level of miR-141 after 5 days in prostatectomy cohort when compared to health controls.	Egidi et al	2013
miR-141, and 26a-1	Serum	Two prospective cohorts, first with 54 patients with positive PrCa biopsy, and 79 with negative PrCa biopsy	Qiagen RT-qPCR	MIRNAs were similar in patients with positive and negative biopsies. Significant elevation of miR-141 in patients with higher Gleason Score. miR-141 detectable in healthy controls and BPH pts.	Westermann et al	2014
miR-141, 21, and 221	Plasma	25 mPrCa patients, 26 localized PrCa patients, and 20 healthy controls	Qiagen RT-qPCR	MIR-141 degree of elevation could be used to differentiate patients with localized PrCa from those with mPrCa	Agaoglu et al	2011
miR-141	Plasma	Retrospective cohort of 21 mPrCa patients receiving standard therapy	Qiagen RT-qPCR	Elevated miR-141 strongly correlated with poor prognosis, temporal changes of PSA, LDH, and CTCs	Gonzales et al	2013
miR-141, 126, 151-3p, 152, 200c, 375, and 423-3p	EDTA- Plasma	25 mPrCa patients and 25 localized PrCa patients	Exiqon array and RT-qPCR	Degree of elevation of miRNAs could differentiate localized from mPrCa patients	Watahiki et al	2013
miR-141, 30c, 375, and let-7c	EDTA- Plasma	59 PrCa patients at many ranges, 16 BPH patients, and 11 healthy controls	Qiagen RT-qPCR	Degree of depressed levels of miRNA could differentiate PrCa from BPH and healthy controls	Kachakova et al	2015
miR-141, 145, 155, and let-7a	EDTA- Plasma	75 PrCa patients and 27 patients with negative prostate biopsy	TaqMan RT-qPCR	Degree of variance from mean miRNA levels in patients with benign prostate biopsy was shown to correlate with poor prognosis	Kelly et al	2015
miR-141, miR-375, miR-107, miR-574-3p	Serum exosomes	Initial study of 78 patients with PrCa compared with 28 healthy men. Validation cohort of 47 patients with recurrence post-prostatectomy and 72 patients without recurrence	TaqMan RT-qPCR	mPrCa successfully differentiated from non-metastatic PrCa by screening for increase in miR-141 and miR-375.	Bryant et al	2012
miR-141	Whole serum and serum exosomes	Comparison of 31 patients with mPrCa, 20 non-metastatic PrCa, and 40 healthy controls	Takara RT-qPCR	Increased concentration of miR-141 in serum and exosomes could be used to differentiate localized PrCa from healthy controls as well as differentiate localized PrCa patients from mPrCa. Positive biopsy could be predicted based on miR-141 elevation from both serum and exosomes.	Li et al	2016

Table 2: Summary of a selected series of discoveries and discrepancies that have served as landmarks in the field of cfmiR-141 and PrCa, grouped according to the bodily fluid being collected for study and further organized by year in which the findings were published. Information regarding each publication were collected and reported information includes: miRNA(s) under study, details of the patient population under study, method utilized for quantifying cfmiRNA, significant findings in regards to cfmiR-141 that were reported in the publications, and reference.^{22, 115, 112, 116, 117, 118, 119, 114, 120, 121, 122, 123, 124. 125. 126}

What all of these studies tend to agree with is that cfmiR-141 is strongly associated with poor prognostic indicators. It is unclear whether there is a direct or indirect relationship between cfmiR-141 and PrCa outcomes, but nonetheless there appears to be enough support for the development of a prognostic biomarker with current data. It is possible that elevated cfmiR-141 is not only due to PrCa but may also be product of hemolysis¹¹⁴ or even release of cfmiRNA from B cells, T cells, or dendritic cells whether they be healthy or responding in some way to physiological stress.¹²⁷ Utilizing cfmiR-141 as a prognostic biomarker would be uniquely valuable in the clinic because it does not indicate an exact biological mechanism by which late stage PrCa is causing poor clinical outcomes, but rather providing a generalizable indicator of systematic disease and the outcomes that often accompany such a disease according to many years of compiled data on the matter.

In contrast to the promise of a prognostic tool arising from findings summarized in Table 2, there is much less hope for immediate development of diagnostic tools for PrCa. As indicated by Table 2, those teams who studied cfmiR-141 before the report by Edigi et al¹¹⁹ in 2013, with exception of Brase et al, had continually supported that cfmiR-141 was significantly elevated in the serum of patients with advanced PrCa. Like Brase et al, Edigi et al implemented different analytical methods for quantifying cfmiR-141 reported contrasting results. Edigi et al implemented an Exiqon RT-qPCR kit for cfmiR-141 quantification whereas all of the studies reporting elevated cfmiR-141 in serum beforehand utilized TaqMan RT-qPCR. This may have altered the findings of Edigi et al. Recent reviews^{28,45} point to methodological incongruencies as a likely reason for a high level of discordant results in microarray analysis and RT-qPCR analysis of cfmiRNA in PrCa. Although Westermann et al also implemented a different RT-qPCR kit for sample miRNA

quantification, they demonstrated a high level of particularity in experimental design and shed doubt on the source of cfmiR-141 that was being detected in previous studies. None of the findings can confidently be ruled out due to methodological or analytical errors or limitations; therefore alternative reasons for conflicting results should be entertained.

Together, results from Edigi et al and Westermann et al suggested that the source of cfmiR-141 may not be from the diseased prostate tissue itself, but rather that there may be a systematic response to PrCa, especially mPrCa, in the body that is resulting in cfmiR-141 elevation in serum. Interestingly, Bryant et al¹²⁴ and Li et al¹²⁶ reported a similar signature of elevated cfmiR-141 in the serum exosomes of patients with late-stage and mPrCa. Although the findings by Bryant et al and Li et al do not answer the question as to where cfmiR-141 originated, they seem to have been on right the track to determining such. Arroyo and colleagues caution that AGO2 and lipoprotein complexes with which cfmiRNA are commonly observed tend to co-isolate with EVs when procedures such as ultracentrifugation are implemented, shedding doubt on previous claims in literature regarding EV-RNA content.^{26,107}

Park et al has recently tuned in to the debate by further validating the use of cfmiR-141, particularly prostasome cfmiR-141, as a prognostic tool.⁸² Furthermore, Park et al used convincing visual methods such as transmission electron microscopy (TEM), immuno-TEM with CD63 and prostate-specific membrane antigen (PSMA), and immunofluorescence staining to demonstrate that PrCa is hypervesicular, increasingly so with the progression of PrCa from low to high risk. Park et al went on to describe both intracellular and extracellular vesicles thought to contain miRNA signatures, although they mention that even in hypervesicular high-risk PrCa

shown to secrete the highest level of prostasomes into the circulation were difficult to detect due to low concentrations. Due to the highly various nature of cancer and the proteins it expresses during random mutagenesis, it is unlikely that all cancer derived prostasomes will express a single immunological molecule for detection and isolation according to methods described by Park et al. Regardless, assuming that a particular molecular profile of immunological signals common to the exterior of a prostaosome can be detected an implemented to effectively pull down prostasomes from a biological sample, the field would certainly need to follow up the studies of Bryant et al, Li et al, and Park et al with additional methodology in order to determine the efficacy of not only isolating prostasomes from PrCa tissue but also analyze their contents.

The study of cfmiR-141 has also been subject to criticism because miR-141 is not a prostate specific miRNA, much like PSA may not be cancer-specific. The detection of prostasomes with miR-141 from healthy patients compared to cancer patients would not only provide tissue specific analysis of the miR-141 content, but also cancer-specific detection. In order to undoubtedly refute some of the criticism in the field about the role of cfmiR-141 in PrCa, investigators would need to isolate prostasomes throughout PrCa advancement and analyze their contents. Fiella and Foj reported in recent reviews of PrCa biomarkers that reasonably attainable methods can be adapted with currently available resources to detect prostate-specific EVs and their contents.^{45,46}

Next steps in cfmiR-141 studies

Investigators need to accurately identify the source of cfmiR-141 and either prove or disprove that cfmiR-141 is from prostate cancer tissue, blood, or immune cells in circulation. Before clinically useful diagnostic tools can be fully developed, the field also needs to continue investigating the function of miR-141 intracellularly, prostatesome bound intracellularly, prostatesome bound extracellularly, and the potential function that cfmiR-141 is thought to convey after prostatesomes are absorbed out of the circulation and into cellular contents of a separate tissue type than that which the prostatesome originated from. It would be expected that biomarkers could be developed from knowledge gained during the study of each of these factors in the context of patients with a healthy prostate and those with a range of severity of PrCa, although the field is far from this point. Some of the major challenges in the design of diagnostic tools using cfmiR-141 signatures will be creating precise study designs (general workflow presented in Figure 7), financial challenges, quantification and data analysis challenges, and facing ethical issues.

Figure 7: A workflow model for designing follow up studies of cfmiR-141

Figure caption: Workflow depicting follow up studies to reject or accept the hypothesis that detectable cfmiR-141 is encapsulated in prostasomes obtained from human patients with late-stage – mPrCa. Arrows indicate steps.

Illustration further depicts the process of biomarker discovery and identification in the case that prostasomes prove to be useful clinically. Illustration adapted from *Nat Rev Urol.* 2014 Dec;11(12):688-701.¹²⁸

Urinary EVs which are likely to be prostate-derived have been detected and hold promise as non-invasively obtained biomarkers in PrCa. Although bioinformatics tools are becoming more capable and accessible to clinicians and discoveries such as the biomarker value of urinary prostasomes have been revealed, there are still technical and financial challenges in designing large studies of cfmiRNA that shed doubt on progress for the field.⁴⁵ A study conducted in 2016 that led to the privatization of a current clinical tool for prostate cancer staging that utilizes urine exosomes appears to incorporate depression of cfmiR-141 in urine exosomes as a signature of advanced PrCa in comparison to healthy men.¹²⁹ Again, discrepancies in the field demonstrate the methodological and analytical challenges that researchers face while studying cfmiRNAs. These discrepancies may also shed light on the complexities of cfmiRNA excretion and regulation both intracellularly and extracellularly. The current state of the field of cfmiRNAs demonstrates that there is still much to be discovered. Many researchers have proposed interesting methodological tools and convincing evidence that cfmiRNAs continue to hold potential as diagnostic and prognostic tools even in the light of much ambiguity.

Furthermore, due to our current understanding of the efficacy of cfmiR-141 in detecting PrCa, large clinical studies to monitor cfmiR-141 levels throughout development, progression, or advancement of PrCa would likely be unethical without implementing medical interventions that have been shown to affect cfmiR-141 and intracellular miR-141 content and thus bias the results of the study.⁸⁷

Although there is discordance in methods, population sampling, and analysis that was likely to alter result of previous studies in the field of cfmiR-141 and PrCa, there are also conceptual errors that have been made by previous research groups. Many previous studies assume that cfmiR-141 reflects intracellular miRNA whereas it has been shown that some miRNA can be selectively exported. Assuming that prostasomes were not generated by the cell to serve an intracellular function, it would be expected that the prostasome content would be vastly different than a random sample of intracellular content of a healthy or cancerous prostate cell. It is the difference in intracellular versus extracellular content that can be expected to serve as valuable diagnostic information as the field of exosomes continue to unveil some of the dynamics of miRNA packaging in the cell. Thus, researchers need to begin analyzing prostasomes as both intracellular and extracellular components simultaneously. In order to advance the technology, the most meaningful studies would be conducted in a clinically realistic setting, and patients would be recruited from biopsy studies for analysis of all biological samples including PrCa tissue (if present in biopsy), urine, and blood simultaneously. The high “pay-off” in health, healthcare economics, and knowledge in the scientific community warrants investigation of this form.

Recent studies have found significant downregulation of miR-141 in urine of pts with localized PrCa. This finding was utilized in part as a miRNA signature for localized PrCa as a prognostic model.¹³⁰ Urine based models such as these are recently gaining much attention and some teams have begun developing and selling kits for clinical use even though there is still controversy in the field around the diagnostic value of cfmiRNAs in bodily fluids. In contrast, many of these

models seem to be removing miR-141 from analysis due to a lack of detectability, suggesting that miR-141 may be differentially secreted into the blood and urine.

Discussion

The scientific community response to a need for mPrCa biomarkers

The biomarker will only be valuable if there is evidence that it will have higher sensitivity, specificity, or earlier detection than current biomarkers and imaging tools. The U.S. FDA published information on cancer screening demonstrates the need and trials actively seeking better screening procedures and more effective therapeutic options.

A summary of U.S. FDA reports on clinical trials regarding the investigation of biomarkers, cancer, and metastasis demonstrate a discrepancy between the need for better clinical tools to address metastatic disease in cancer, and the number of clinical trials investigating the issue.

Figure 8: An analysis of FDA and CME approved clinical trials implementing cfmiRNA

Figure 8: Bars represent the number of clinical trials reported by the FDA (*ClinicalTrials.gov* query: circulating miRNA AND cancer; Metastasis; Biomarker; accessed: April 2017). Note that each group of studies is contained within the next more specific grouping query. The majority of studies in each group are active/recruiting.

Percentage breakdown to demonstrate that of the biomarkers being developed in the clinical setting, cancer alone constitutes most, and metastasis encompasses about 30% of that, although 90% of cancer deaths involve metastasis.¹³¹ This depicts the need for basic science investigations into the etiology of metastasis, and effective ways of detecting and preventing metastatic cancer. Two of the studies in the cancer group are currently implementing cfmiR-141 as a secondary outcome variable and there are no current studies utilizing cfmiR-141 as a primary outcome variable.

Biomarker potential of miRNAs

Biomarker Combination:

It is also possible that miR-141 may have a number of different roles in regulating cellular functions or communicating regulatory messages/effects much like hormones, that it would have to be used as a much more general biomarker than current studies have suggested. MiR-141 appears to have different roles in different tissues^{73,74,76} and therefore it may be difficult to determine the significance of an increased cfmiR-141 level for instance, without a much more comprehensive view of the patient condition and environmental determinants of their pathophysiological state, as suggested by Kenneth Witwer.²⁸ Witwer also suggests that a potential solution to the problem of cfmiR-141 serving as a general biomarkers of potentially many regulatory pathways gone awry, would be the isolation of cfmiRNA in conjunction with

another biomarker that indicates tissue-of-origin such as prostasomes. CfmiR-375 should be considered for pairing in biomarker design as it has continually been shown to be detectable in serum analysis often in the same fashion which cfmiR-141 is elevated. CfmiR-375 elevation may give a glimpse into the nucleus- insight to the ZEB1/2 axis because miR-141 thought to repress ZEB1 that represses miR-375.^{117,132} As discussed above, miR-200s can co-regulate and therefore it is also important to include those in analysis of prostatic content because some of the miR-200s may act as pre-cursors to miR-141 after entering a cell, for example. When analyzing prostatic content, it is important to remember that miR-141 detection may constitute detection of pre-miR-141 or double stranded miR-141-3p with miR-141-5p. Extrapolating momentarily, just the presence of a reverse transcriptase and a 5p segment of miR-141 may suffice to convey function in distant cells if one were to consider an analogous viral infectious-type miRNA model. Furthermore, inability to detect miRNA in an exosome, or detection of abnormal miRNA precursors or processing enzymes illustrated in Figures 3 and 4, may also give insight as to the state of the tissue which cfmiRNA are sourced.

Some problems with isolation of tissue derived EVs is that the means by which they are tested could damage the already low-moderately abundant miRNA that they contain.²² It has also been shown that tissue-specific EVs constitute very little of the miRNA in circulation that is commonly reported in studies in the field such as those mentioned in Table 2. Recent studies in the field of intracellular miR-141 by Li et al and Liu et al further complicate the issue by reporting differential regulation and function of miR-141 wherein effects of miR-141 function such as EMT suppression, regulation of suppression, and regulation of cytoskeletal proteins could increase or decrease cfmiRNA in the circulation (as depicted in Figure 5). The

heterogeneous nature of cancer is continuing to baffle researchers and discrepancies such as those mentioned above continue to fuel controversy in the field.

Potential Biological Sources of Variability in MiR-141 Detection

Chemotherapy

Yao et al demonstrated that miR-141 may be a crucial player in the development chemotherapy resistance in patients with breast cancer by means of miRNA-mediated inhibition of eukaryotic translation initiation factor 4E mRNA, essentially eliminating an expressional pathway that is targeted by chemotherapy drugs in order to induce apoptosis.¹³³ This study adds to the literature showing that chemotherapy can directly induce bias in a study of cfmiRNA.⁸⁷

Changes in cfmiRNA due to exercise and diet

There have been obvious connections made between cfmiRNA and blood/cardiac cells and therefore it is not surprising that physical exercise, known to stress cardiac tissue to some degree, can effect cfmiRNA levels. Sapp et al¹³⁴ go on to also suggest that changes in oxygenation of blood affect many organs that then respond by releasing cfmiRNA. Furthermore, Guescini et al demonstrated that skeletal muscle increased EV secretion of miRNA from a baseline level during skeletal muscle resting to elevated levels upon exercise.¹³⁵

Some studies¹³⁶ have argued that miRNA can be consumed by plant or dairy products and enter the circulation at detectable levels, which is likely to have physiological consequences although this has not been investigated thoroughly and new computational analysis of large datasets suggest that dietary miRNA (xenomirs) could be technical artifacts.¹³⁷ Nonetheless, the “*Dietary*

MicroRNA Database (DMD): An Archive Database and Analytic Tool for Food-Borne microRNAs” has been developed and continues to gain data from researchers actively investigating the topic, demonstrating the confidence that researchers have in regards to the reality of the phenomenon.¹³⁸ Little has been discussed in the realm of dietary miRNA, or the effects of diet on miRNA expression in human tissues and the current data do not seem to warrant further analysis of dietary cfmiRNA expression profiles until more sensitive analytical methods of miRNA detection are developed. Currently, a more approachable area of study may include the effect of diet on gastrointestinal microbiota, and the ability of those microbiota to influence miRNA expression in the gastrointestinal tissues including EV encapsulation and release of miRNA signals into serum.⁷⁴ Xenomir research currently seems to be an area in the field of cfmiRNAs of great contention.

Interestingly though, It may be argued that if humans can potentially absorb miRNA from environmental sources, it is likely that humans are also excreting miRNA into the environment for uptake or recycling. Interactions between organisms, their genetic information, and the environment in which they interact may have far fewer boundaries than we have previously postulated. Genetic information in the form of small RNA molecules being recycled may constitute a much more important role in human than previously thought. These areas of research are not only challenging how scientists view the way we interact, affect, and are affected by our environment, but also further complicates the problems of using miRNA as biomarkers.

Evolution by miRNA

In studying miRNA- some of the smallest, most highly conserved, and likely some of the most fundamental regulatory molecules in a cell- there is always the possibility that we are actively observing some of the biomolecular events of evolution. For example, mutations that accommodate miRNA targeting, or inhibit binding of a previously targeted mRNA, may be an evolutionary processes taking place in humans currently. This could explain some, although not likely all, of the discrepancies in miRNA functioning since the start of its discovery and proceeding studies. Generally speaking, environmental factors that have changed over the course of 10 years could be shaping the mutagenic causing agents or stressors that lead to PrCa, thereby changing the miRNA regulatory networks involved in cellular homeostasis. The effect of time on cancer biology would be difficult to demonstrate, yet deserves consideration in the study of PrCa. More evident is the change in PrCa and the change in miRNA regulatory networks due to more advanced chemotherapies. It has been demonstrated that miR-141 may be involved in doctaxel resistant PrCa,¹³³ which can be thought of as a chemotherapy that has entered the market and affected any PrCa tumor that was unsuccessfully treated with the drug. The ability of cancer to evade chemotherapy can be thought of as an evolutionary event in which the cancer cell is altered at a genomic level, which is shown to play a critical role in cancer survival.

Regardless of valuable insights that the study of miRNA have instigated, the ability of cancerous tumors to evade targeted therapies has demonstrated the dynamic and complex nature of cancer survival, and continued to challenge researchers and clinicians to understand the disease.

In application, no biomarker gives you certain results and biomarkers are commonly used as tools in medical decision making while much more information about the patient condition is

available. One problem facing the prostate oncologists is an imprecise screening procedure in which PSA and DRE are the readily available, yet unreliable⁴² source of information for prostate cancer diagnosis. Due to inefficient screening tools, many unnecessary and potentially dangerous prostate biopsies are conducted annually.⁴² If a biomarker such as prostatesome encapsulated miRNA, could provide some indication of prostate cancer development or progression, it would be expected that such technological advancements would save many resources, much time, and provide a greater sense of security in patients and healthcare providers that prostate cancer is being properly screened, diagnosed, staged, and treated.

In summary, a unidirectional model to explain miRNA functioning in vivo is simply insufficient and inaccurate. Many studies have now demonstrated that many miRNA, including miR-141, respond to stress and environmental conditions. MiRNAs have continually refined the way in which scientists view the complex regulatory networks of molecular biology that dictate human health and the interplay of humans in their environment, and thus a new model of tridirectional interplay (illustrated in Figure 9) of miRNAs should replace that of the conventional model (Figure 2) in order to more accurately describe the highly-conserved, deep-rooted nature miRNA in human health.

Figure 9 : A new model of dynamic miRNA regulation and human health

Figure 9: Dynamic interplay of miRNA source and biological results

Future of MiRNA Biomarkers in Prostate Cancer Diagnosis

An efficient and standardized method of isolating prostasomes would likely revolutionize personalized medicine in which targeted therapies would be directed for transcriptional targets, somewhere in between the commonly protein targets of chemotherapies and the gene abnormalities treated by CRISPR. Delivery of a therapy such as miR-interference or miR-activation/replacement would soon need to be investigated and it may be thought that synthetic prostasomes could potentially have higher affinity for prostate than current delivery exosomes.

The evidence is attractive, if not convincing, that there truly is a biological underpinning of the associations noticed between cfmiR-141, late stage PrCa, and metastatic PrCa. Although we may not have the tools currently, the field can expect to see development of new analytical methods that are highly specialized such as polymerase enzymes that are biochemically altered in a way that their processivity, proofreading abilities, accuracy, and integrity in PCR solutions used for cfmiRNA collection are optimally designed for cfmiR-141. RT-qPCR methods would be specific for miR-141, enabling extremely high accuracy in detecting the exact level to which miR-141 is elevated, for example. Such specialized RT-qPCR polymerases would be expected to become the standard in the field and allow for better comparison of results between studies.

This further suggests that conventional methods for determining miR-141 targets in prostate tissue may in some way need refinement. The challenge of determining dysregulated signaling in PrCa for diagnostic purposes may be directed to the field of bioinformatics, data processing, and machine learning. In order for proper deferment of the challenge to take place though, analytical methods for precise measurement of intracellular and extracellular miR-141 need to be adapted for quick computational input.

Precise biomarker development is necessary in order to accurately target future miRNA or RNAi based therapies for PrCa. The field needs to form a better understanding of source and function of cfmiRNA before progressing with miRNA targeted therapies in PrCa. It would not be unethical to withhold resources from therapy development in order to better develop prognostic and diagnostic tools for cancer. With knowledge of the etiology of a disease such as mPrCa, current therapies can be targeted more deliberately at earlier stages of prostate cancer progression, having a direct an immediate effect on patient health and survival.

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